

Investigating the Influence of English on Balochi, Following the Colonization of Balochistan: Morphology (Bamoshti dialect; a subdialect of Sarawani dialect)

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Abstract

There are not many words in Balochi which have analogous equivalents in English, but even the small numbers of them make people think there is a relationship between the two languages of Balochi and English. This research aimed to investigate if the colonization of Balochistan had an impact on the Balochi language (Bamoshti dialect) in the case of morphology. There are not many words in Bamoshti Balochi which have equivalents in English being similar to them in terms of pronunciation; 18 of these words were investigated in this research. The investigation on these words revealed a shocking result. Only 4 (%22.2) of the words which were investigated on, found to be English loanwords. The data collected in this research proves the idea that there is a relationship between Balochi and English in the case of morphology. It also proves that the colonization of Balochistan is the reason of which Balochi has English words (loanwords).

Keywords: Balochi, English, Colonization, Morphology

1. Introduction

Language communicates culture and summarizes a country's beliefs, values, thoughts, and oral literature. We perceive ourselves and our places in the world through language, culture, and identity. Colonizers tend to impose their languages on conquered populations because of the close link between language and identity (Sayedayn, 2021).

1.1. Balochi

The Balochi language belongs to one of the Iranian branches of the Aryan family, which is called 'Baloch' (Longworth Dames, 1881). Balochi is spoken by a considerable number of people in Karachi, Balochistan, and lesser numbers in Punjab and Sindh of Pakistan. It is also

spoken in the province of Sistan and Baluchistan in south-eastern Iran, and Baloch who have settled in the north-eastern regions of Khorasan and Golestan. It is even spoken by smaller populations in Afghanistan, the Gulf States (particularly Oman and the United Arab Emirates), Turkmenistan's Marw/ Mari region, India, East Africa, and more recently, by a significant number of Baloch in North America, Europe, and Australia(Windfuhr, 2009). The dialect in which this research is concentrated is spoken insouth-eastern part of Sistan and Baluchistan province of Iran. Balochi language is spoken in many nations worldwide, and it has socio-linguistic ties to other languages. It interacts with Persian, Arabic, Pashto, Turkmen, Sindhi, Punjabi, English, and other European and African languages in modern times(Baloch, 2012).

Colonizers seek indigenous or non-Western identities by influencing indigenous languages to take over the minds, thoughts, and values of those they colonize. Language is used to transmit ideas and views discreetly but effectively. This linguistic policy allows conquerors to continue colonizing while also strengthening the colonized lands' roots (Sayedayn, 2021).

Before the 18th century, there was no sign of colonial power in the close surrounding area of Balochistan. As Dashti (2012) states: "Dark clouds engulfed the Baloch state from "The Great Game" being played in Central Asia by Russia, France, and England—a treacherous game which had begun in the eighteenth century". Years later, Balochistan's (Khanate of Kalat's) situation got complicated by the British's presence in Afghanistan and Sindh. At that time, the Khan (Balochistan's head leader) had to sign a treaty with the British to avoid conflict (Dashti, 2012).

Britain's primary motivation for signing a pact with the Khanate of Kalat was to offer a route and supplies to the "Army of Indus" on its approach to Kandahar (Afghanistan) via Balochistan. It's worthy to note that, unlike other parts of India, the British colonial ambitions in Balochistan were not primarily economic. It had more of a military and geopolitical nature than anything else. When they arrived in Balochistan, their main goal was to place military bases to defend British India's borders against any threat from Iran and Afghanistan. They also wanted to make Balochistan the first line of defense in the event of a Russian thrust into India, create a safe zone between themselves and rival colonial military aggression arising from the French and Russians, and find safe passage through the area in the event of military escalation. The Baloch state was ultimately the victim of this process (Dashti, 2012).

- What made the British invade Balochistan?

Whenthe Army of Indus and supplies were en route to Kandahar, one of the Baloch tribes attacked them, and the leader of that tribe made the British officials believe that the Khan was secretly asking the tribes to stop the Army of Indus (Dashti, 2012).

After the defeat of the Afghan ruler in Kandahar and placing the new ruler by the British Army, a part of the Army returned to Quetta (Balochistan). Now, The British could focus their attention on Kalat and punish the Khan for not abiding by the treaty, which they had already illegally revoked without even informing the Khan.And eventually, in November of 1839,

British took over the capital, and Kalat fell (Dashti, 2012). And this was the starting point of the colonial era of Balochistan.

Only a little Valid research has been conducted on the Balochi language in its history, and most of them are from the 1970s and after that. Josef Elflein and Carina Jahani have made a significant contribution to modern Balochi language research (Spooner, 2012). Most of their work is focused on the construction of Balochi.

In Iran, in the Educational System of Government, students start to learn English at thirteen (Secondary school). As learning English goes on, some Baloch students start to ask: “*why do I feel like I know some of these words from before?!*”; And this is where they start “*the search*” to solve the mystery. Some, in days, and others find the answer to the question after months. The answer they find is “Balochi”; they find out that they have many words in their own language (Balochi) which are similar to English words and also convey the same meaning.

At the same time they find the answer to their mystery, another question raises in their minds: “*why Balochi has so many common words with English?*”. After passing a series of History courses, those interested enough to continue thinking on the subject found out that the *Colonization* seemed to be the answer. But is it true? This research aims to find the answer to this question.

The fact that there are not many valid resources (such as books, journals, or articles) available in the libraries makes working on this subject more challenging.

1.2. English

The English language is a member of the West Germanic subdivision of the Indo-European language family. English is the official language of about 45 countries and is spoken by around 470 million people worldwide. It is the mother tongue of approximately 60 million people in the British Isles, from which it extended to many other regions of the world as a result of British exploration, Colonization, and empire-building between the 17th and 19th centuries. It is currently the first language of about 228 million people in the United States, 16.5 million in Canada, 17 million in Australia, 3 million in New Zealand and a number of Pacific islands, as well as about 15 million in other countries of the Western Hemisphere, Africa, and Asia. As a result of this expansion, English is now the most frequently spoken language around the world. It is also the world’s most widely used auxiliary language. The United Nations utilizes English as one of its two working languages (The Columbia Electronic Encyclopedia, n.d.).

1.3. Morphology

Morphology comes from the Greek word *morphos*, which means “shape”. It studies the internal composition and structure of words as well as the patterns and rules underlying their composition. As a result, Morphology is considered the traditional barrier between grammar

and lexicon(Schmid, 2015). Studying Morphology is a broad field, but in this research, the focus is on: *Nouns, Verbs, Adjectives, and Adverbs.*

Research Question

If the Colonization is the reason for which Balochi has similar words to English, “*To what extent Balochi has been changed as a result of Balochistan being colonized by the British?*”

Hypothesis

There is NO relationship between Balochi and English in the case of Morphology.

2. Methodology

2.1. Materials

Materials used to carry out the research were Articles, Journals, and Books.

2.2. Procedures

2.2.1. Data collection

This research is conducted using the Qualitative method. The data is collected through Observation.

All the data (Texts; No statistical data) in this research have been taken from Primary and Secondary sources; Sources such as Textbooks, Journal Articles, Results of research, Encyclopaedias’, and Observation.

Base data was obtained using Observation. First step was to find out ‘How many similar words’ there are between Bamposhti Balochi & English and ‘what are they?’. Next, the data were extracted and brought to study. Studying data (words) was difficult as there are Few sources about Balochi words and their Etymology. A dozen words were eliminated using the few sources available as there was no information about them. The remaining words went under deeper study.

3. Findings

Abbreviations

Ar.	Arabic
Av.	Avestan
Bal.	Balochi
Bam.	Bamposhti dialect
Engl.	English

EngEnglish

Europ.	European
Ind.	Indic
Ir.	Iranian
NP	New Persian
OAv.	Old Avestan
OInd.	Old Indic (Vedic, Sanscrit)
Si.	Sindhi
Ur.	Urdu
BBal.	Bamoshti Balochi

Symbols

-oubles the vocal intensity of the letter that came before it (e.g., a⁻ = aa)

-cuts the voice immediately

Definitions

Loanword: a word taken from another language and at least partly naturalized (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, n.d.).

Data

The following table contains data about some of the words in BBal. which have analogous equivalents in English.

Balochi word "pronunciation"	Equivalent	Analogous word in English	Category in Morphology	Etymology:	Reference
استار "Estar"	Star	<i>Star</i>	Noun	1. Ir /Av 2. OInd. 3. NP star- stár- sit ⁻ ara	Korn, 2003: 261
برات "Baat"	Brother	<i>Brother</i>	Noun	bra ⁻ tar bhra ⁻ tr- bara ⁻ dar	Korn, 2003: 268

بَس "Bas"	Bus	Bus	Noun	NP: utubu ⁻ s	*Europ. (Engl.) Loanword Korn, 2003: 270 Elfenbein,1990:23
بَسْت / بَند "Band / Bast"	Bind	Bind	Noun	band- / basta- badh band- / bast	Korn, 2003: 271
تَيْبَل "Tibal"	Table	Table	Noun	_	* Europ. (Engl.) loanword Korn, 2003: 283
جَنگَل "Jangal"	Forest	Jungle	Noun	jangal	* Ind. Loanword Korn, 2003: 284
دَتگ "Dottag"	Daughter	Daughter	Noun	OAv. duyedar- duhitár- duxt, duxtar	Korn, 2003: 290
دِيوَال "Diwaal"	Wall	Wall	Noun	NP: di ⁻ wa ⁻ r	* NP loanword (via Ur.) Korn, 2003: 294 Elfenbein,1990:43
دَاكْثَر "Daakthar"	Doctor	Doctor	Noun	_	* Europ. (Engl.) loanword (via Ur.) Korn, 2003: 294
رَوْتگ "Routag"	Root	Root	Noun	_	Korn, 2003: 296
سِمِث "Semeth"	Cement	Cement	Noun	_	* Europ. (Engl.) loanword Korn, 2003: 303
شَكَر / شَكَل "Shakar / Shakkal"	Sugar	Sugar	Noun	NP: šakar	* NP-Ar. Loanword Korn, 2003: 307 Elfenbein, 1990: 141

لڏ	Load	<i>Load</i>	Verb	–	* <i>Ind. (Si.)</i> <i>loanword</i> Korn, 2003: 325
“Ladd”					
لنگ	Leg	<i>Leg</i>	Noun	NP: ling	* <i>NP loanword</i> Korn, 2003: 325 Elfenbein, 1990:92
“Leng”					
ليمبو	Lemon	<i>Lemon</i>	Noun	NP: li ⁻ mbo ⁻	* <i>NP loanword</i> Korn, 2003: 326 Elfenbein, 1990: 91
“Limbo”					
مات	Mother	<i>Mother</i>	Noun	ma ⁻ tar ma ⁻ tr- ma ⁻ dar	Korn, 2003: 326
“Maat”					
نون	Now	<i>Now</i>	Adverb	nu ⁻ rem nu ⁻ nám nu ⁻ n	Korn, 2003: 334
“Noon”					
هڪ	Egg	<i>Egg</i>	Noun	NP: xa ⁻ ya	* <i>NP loanword</i> Korn, 2003: 341
“Heik”					

4. Discussion

The collected Basedata gave the impression that a vast majority of Baloch people believe that “*Colonization* had an impact on *Balochi* language”. As of this, the efforts in this study are focused on finding if this belief is true or not.

The Basedata, which were obtained via Observation, contained 35 words. As mentioned in previous parts, there are not many valid resources for Balochi; even these valid resources do not cover Balochi words entirely as it is vast, unwritten, and has many dialects. As a result, only 18 of these 35 words could be found in available dictionaries.

Findings show that in some cases, the analogy between some of the words in Balochi, especially Bamposhti Balochi and English, comes from **Loanwords**. Some of these loanwords come directly from English (*Europ.(Eng.)*), some from other languages, such as *Ar., Ind., NP, Ur., & Si.*, some do NOT have a specific known source language.

✚ Here is the analysis of words and their Etymology (by Balochi alphabet order):

1. استار (Estaar):

This word is similar to the English word “Star”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Star”.

~ Etymology:

There are three possible known roots for this word according to Korn (2003):

First: *Ir. (Iranian)* root = star-

Second: *OInd. (Old Indic)* root = stár-

Third: *NP (New Persian)* root = sit⁻ara

According to this information, the word “استار” DOES NOT come from **English**.

2. بُرات (Braat):

This word is similar to the English word “Brother”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Brother”.

~ Etymology:

There are three possible known roots for this word according to Korn (2003):

First: *Ir. (Iranian)* root = bra⁻tar

Second: *OInd. (Old Indic)* root = bhra⁻tr-

Third: *NP (New Persian)* root = bara⁻dar

According to this information, the word “بُرات” DOES NOT come from **English**.

3. بَس (Bas):

This word is similar to the English word “Bus”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Bus”.

~ Etymology:

There is one possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003) & Elfenbein (1990):

NP (New Persian) root = utubu⁻s

Although the word “بَس” has only one known root, and it's from New Persian, it's a **European (English) Loanword**.

According to this information, the word “بَس” DOES come from **English**.

4. بَسْت / بَند (Band / Bast):

This word is similar to the English word “Bind”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Bind”.

~ Etymology:

There are three possible known roots for this word according to Korn (2003):

First: *Ir. (Iranian)* root = band- / basta

Second: *OInd. (Old Indic)* root = badh

Third: *NP (New Persian)* root = band- / bast

According to this information, the word “بَسْت / بَند” DOES NOT come from **English**.

5. تَيْبِل (Tibal):

This word is similar to the English word “Table”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Table”.

~ Etymology:

There is no possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003)

The word “تَيْبِل” is a **European (English) Loanword**.

According to this information, the word “تَيْبِل” DOES come from **English**.

6. جنگل(Jangal):

This word is similar to the English word “Jungle”; its equivalent in English is “Forest”.

~ Etymology:

There is one possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003):

Ir (Iranian) root = jangal

Although the word “جنگل” has only one known root and it’s from New Persian, it’s an **Indic Loanword**.

According to this information, the word “جنگل” DOES NOT come from **English**.

7. دُتگ(Dottag):

This word is similar to the English word “Daughter”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Daughter”.

~ Etymology:

There are three possible known roots for this word according to Korn (2003):

First: *OAv. (Old Avestan)* root = duyedar-

Second: *OInd. (Old Indic)* root = duhitár-

Third: *NP (New Persian)* root = duxt, duxtár

According to this information, the word “دُتگ” DOES NOT come from **English**.

8. دیوال(Diwaal):

This word is similar to the English word “Wall”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Wall”.

~ Etymology:

There is one possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003) & Elfenbein (1990):

NP (New Persian) root = di-wa-r

According to this information, the word “دیوال” DOES NOT come from **English**; it’s a **New Persian Loanword**.

9. ڈاکٹر(Daaktar):

This word is similar to the English word “Doctor”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Doctor”.

~ Etymology:

There is no possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003);

The word “ڈاکٹر” is a *European (English) Loanword*.

According to this information, the word “ڈاکٹر” DOES come from **English**.

10. روتگ(Routag):

This word is similar to the English word “Root”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Root”.

~ Etymology:

There is no possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003).

According to this information, we cannot say if the word “روتگ” DOES come from English or NOT. (?)

11. سِمٹ(Semeth): This word is similar to the English word “Cement”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Cement”.

~ Etymology:

There is no possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003);

The word “سِمِٹ” is a **European (English) Loanword**.

According to this information, the word “سِمِٹ” DOES come from **English**.

12. شَكَّر / شَكَّل (Shakar / Shakkal):

This word is similar to the English word “Sugar”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Sugar”.

~ Etymology:

There is one possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003)&Elfenbein (1990):

NP (New Persian) root =šakar

According to this information, the word “شَكَّر” DOES NOT come from **English**; it’s a **New Persian – Arabic Loanword**.

13. لَدَّ (Ladd):

This word is similar to the English word “Load”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Load”.

~ Etymology:

There is no possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003);

The word “لَدَّ” is an **Indic (Sindhi) Loanword**.

According to this information, the word “لَدَّ” DOES NOT come from **English**.

14. لِنَگ (Leng):

This word is similar to the English word “Leg”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Leg”.

~ Etymology:

There is one possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003)&Elfenbein (1990):

NP (New Persian) root =ling

According to this information, the word “لِنَگ” DOES NOT come from **English**; it’s a **New Persian Loanword**.

15. لِيْمْبُو (Limbo):

This word is similar to the English word “Lemon”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Lemon”.

~ Etymology:

There is one possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003)&Elfenbein (1990):

NP (New Persian) root =li mbo

According to this information, the word “لِيْمْبُو” DOES NOT come from **English**; it’s a **New Persian Loanword**.

16. مَات (Maat):

This word is similar to the English word “Mother”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Mother”.

~ Etymology:

There are three possible known roots for this word according to Korn (2003):

First: *Ir. (Iranian)* root = ma⁻tar

Second: *OInd. (Old Indic)* root = ma⁻tr –

Third: *NP (New Persian)* root = ma⁻dar

According to this information, the word “بر ات” DOES NOT come from **English**.

17. **نون (Noon):**

This word is similar to the English word “Now”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Now”.

~ Etymology:

There are three possible known roots for this word according to Korn (2003):

First: *Ir. (Iranian)* root = nu⁻rem

Second: *OInd. (Old Indic)* root = nu⁻nám

Third: *NP (New Persian)* root = nu⁻n

According to this information, the word “بر ات” DOES NOT come from **English**.

18. **هئك (Heik):**

This word is similar to the English word “Egg”; its meaning also is as same as that of “Egg”.

~ Etymology:

There is one possible known root for this word according to Korn (2003):

NP (New Persian) root = xa⁻ya

According to this information, the word “هئك” DOES NOT come from **English**; it's a *New Persian Loanword*.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this research was to determine if the *Colonization* of Balochistan had an impact on the *Balochi* language in the case of *Morphology*.

Among the 18 words which are studied in this research,

4 were found to be **European (English)** loanwords;

5 were found to be **Persian** loanwords;

2 were found to be **Indic** loanwords;

6 were found to certainly not be English, as there were different mentioned sources for them;

and 1 didn't have any known source.

According to the data above, as Balochistan is in close contact with several different cultures and languages such as Persian and Indic, its culture and language have been affected by them; one proof for this claim is “Loanwords”. About loanwords from Persian, there are شكر ، هئك ، ليمبو ، لنگ ، ديوال ، and for Indic, لڏ ، جنگل . About English, as the British colonizers were in India at first, and then in Balochistan itself, their presence led to culture/language changes accordingly. A few examples of English loanwords are بس ، ٽيبل ، . ، ڏاڪٽر ، سميٽ .

All of the prior data makes it clear that **THERE IS** a relationship between *Balochi* and *English* in the case of *Morphology*, but not to the extent the public thinks. As in this research, only 4 words (% 22.2) out of 18 words were found to be from the English language.

According to 1. there are English loanwords in Balochi, 2. Balochistan has been a part of the British's colonial territory, and 3. Language is used to transmit ideas and views discreetly but effectively. This linguistic policy allows conquerors to continue colonizing while also strengthening the colonized lands' roots (Sayedayn, 2021); accordingly, it's proven that *English* has influenced *Balochi*(in the case of *Morphology*) following the *Colonization* of Balochistan.

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